

Potential Analysis of Aek Nauli Elephant Conservation in Preserving Biological Natural Resources

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ABSTRACT

Protecting endangered and endangered species by preserving their natural habitat is important today, one way is to do conservation. Wild animals need to be managed properly because protection of animals must be done because their populations are decreasing in the wild. One of the animals that must get attention for its almost extinct habitat is the elephant. It is known that the Sumatran elephant (*Elephas maximus sumatranus*) is on the verge of extinction. Elephants are a key species because of their impact on the environment. Keystone species are species that have a major impact on the environment and can affect ecosystems. The purpose of this research is to find out how the effect of elephant conservation in Aek Nauli Elephant Conservation on living natural resources as an effort to preserve living natural resources. Therefore Habitat conservation for key species has a positive impact on populations for other species because they depend on and share the same type of habitat for their survival.

INTRODUCTION

Wildlife conservation is the act of protecting endangered and endangered species by preserving their natural habitat. Wildlife conservation is also important to do considering that wildlife conservation will encourage the breeding of endangered animal offspring, especially animals that give birth for a long time, so their sustainability is threatened. Activity preservation and protection of animals and their habitats to ensure that future generations can see and know the natural state and the species that live in it. By studying and understanding wildlife ecosystems, we can protect and protect their habitats. The benefits directly and indirectly affect the condition and quality of the environment and humans. Wild animals need to be managed properly because protection of animals must be done because their populations are decreasing in the wild. In fact, every animal has a role for the ecosystem or nature around it. Therefore, animals that experience scarcity must be protected, so that ecosystem changes do not occur.

One of the animals that must get attention for its almost extinct habitat is the elephant. It is known that the Sumatran elephant (*Elephas maximus sumatranus*) is on the verge of extinction. According to KLHK data for 2020, during 2011-2017, the population decreased by 700 individuals. Local extinctions even occurred in more than 20 pockets of habitat. The construction of an elephant conservation center at KHDTK Aek Nauli in North Sumatra is a conservation effort with the aim of increasing opportunities for elephant breeding, genetic preservation, as research objects, as well as utilization for ecotourism purposes.

Through Law Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry, the Government can designate Forest Areas with Special Purposes (KHDTK) for public purposes such as research and development, education and training, as well as religion and culture. Several work units of environmental and forestry research and development centers which are directly under the coordination of the Agency for Research and Development and Innovation for Environment and Forestry, have obtained KHDTK management rights for the purposes of education and training as well as research and development. The KHDTK, which is managed by the Research and Development Agency and Innovation through its work units located in the regions, has strategic value because it has a very important role as a learning medium for forestry research and innovation activities which is used as a reference or research-based government decision-making material. Forest Areas with Special Purposes (KHDTK) Aek Nauli is one of the KHDTK stipulated by Decree of the Minister of Forestry Number 39/Menhut-II/2005 dated 7 February 2005 with an area of 1,900 ha. This area was previously a protected forest.

Apart from providing suitable habitat, the involvement of local communities in terms of Sumatran elephant conservation is very important to determine the success of the HEC mitigation strategy. What needs to be addressed is the awareness of local communities that they play an important role in maintaining a sustainable HEC mitigation strategy. But to do so, it is necessary to ensure that local farmers and communities living in national park areas receive ongoing support and guidance from government agencies and conservation NGOs. In this way, community welfare and Sumatran elephant conservation can be achieved.

The formulation of the problem from this research is how real efforts are made by the government, society and other sectors in protecting wildlife habitat, especially the Sumatran elephant to achieve the preservation of biological natural resources. While the purpose of this research is to find out how the influence of wildlife conservation on living natural resources as a form of effort to preserve living natural resources.

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

The location in the preparation of this article is in Sibaganding Village, Girsang Sipanganbolon District, Simalungun Regency, North Sumatra Province. The choice of North Sumatra Province as the location for the discussion in this paper is due to the fact that there are many Forest Areas with Special Purposes (KHDTK) which are very large and interesting to study. Data used in 101 Journal of Natural Resources and Environment Management⁹(1): 100-104 this research is secondary data. Secondary data in this study included: laws and regulations related to KHDTK management and forest utilization, data and information about the condition of Aek Nauli's KHDTK and other supporting documents.

Data collection was carried out by exploring various literature related to the management of the Aek Nauli Special Purpose Forest Area (KHDTK) through a literature study of the results of research related to the management of the Aek Nauli Special Purpose Forest Area which had been carried out by the Aek Nauli Research and Development Center for Environment and Forestry (BP2LHK).

Data processing and analysis was carried out in a qualitative descriptive manner, namely research that attempted to describe or describe the relationships under study in a systematic, factual and accurate manner. Descriptive analysis of the sustainable management of KHDTK Aek Nauli was obtained based on secondary data searches on documents of Aek Nauli's KHDTK management. This analysis technique aims to determine the characteristics of KHDTK Aek Nauli's sustainable management activities and regulatory issues in the field obtained from content analysis of laws and regulations related to Aek Nauli's KHDTK. Content analysis is a research method used to analyze written documents such as reports, letters and other written forms that are flexible and can be applied to many problems in research information,

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Director General of Natural Resources and Ecosystem Conservation of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Ir. Wiratno, has inaugurated the construction of the tame elephant and primate recreation facility Aek Nauli Elephant Conservation Camp (ANECC), Thursday (7/11/17). This location is in the Forest Area with a Special Purpose (KHDTK), Aek Nauli, Labuhan Batu Regency, North Sumatra (North Sumatra) covering an area of 285 hectares. The area which is now known as the Aek Nauli Elephant Conservation Camp (ANECC) was initiated to preserve the Sumatran elephant (*Elephas maximus sumatranus*) which has a protected conservation status. There are four tame Sumatran elephants (*Elephas maximus sumatranus*) who are the new residents. This endangered animal, imported from the Holiday Resort Elephant Training Center. ANECC, keep improving. The concept of elephant ecotourism was developed. In addition to supporting national priority tourism on Lake Toba, Ecotourism is also an important part of the development of the modern Sumatran elephant conservation concept. The concept of ecotourism in this area

is expected to be an alternative for the development of wildlife conservation programs and at the same time have direct economic value. The concept of ecotourism and the research results of BP2LHK Aek Nauli at ANECC are published in a book. As one of the flagship species which has become a symbol for increasing conservation awareness, the concept of elephant ecotourism can be a strategic matter to garner the participation of many parties. This effort is expected to be a model in realizing sustainable management of forest resources. ANECC is also expected to become an educational tourism object that is able to provide understanding to visitors or tourists to care about the preservation of elephants.

Elephants are a key species because of their impact on the environment. Keystone species are species that have a major impact on the environment and can affect ecosystems. It can be said that ecosystems depend on key species and can change if they become extinct. Elephants eat very much and can weigh up to 300 kg per day. The ability to eat is an advantage for nature and is closely related to interactions with other species. Plants in the forest are eaten by elephants and keep the trees productive. With a large body, elephants roam the forest and pave the way for elephants other animals. Elephants also defecate up to 18 times a day and contribute to nature. Elephant dung can be used as fertilizer to fertilize the soil. Seeds that are eaten and discarded through the excrement will be scattered in nature, embedded in the soil, and the seeds will grow back more quickly. This is because the seeds contained in elephant dung have been processed in the digestive system and have special advantages. Therefore Habitat conservation for key species has a positive impact on populations for other species because they depend on and share the same type of habitat for their survival.

The Sumatran elephant is a subspecies of the Asian elephant that remains in the world with an endangered status and its population continues to decline due to various factors. Therefore, it is important to carry out conservation efforts to protect and preserve the Sumatran elephant. The current population of Sumatran elephants is estimated to have decreased by around 35% from 1992 and this value is a very large decrease in a relatively short time. According to the World Wildlife Fund for Nature-Indonesia (2008) the elephant population with a total of 2400 -2800 individuals is estimated. Many factors have resulted in the decline in the Sumatran elephant population getting out of control. Like illegal logging activities, habitat loss and fragmentation, killings due to conflict and hunting are serious threats that affect the sustainability of these animals. Conflicts between humans and wild animals, especially elephants, continue to increase over time. The government has also created locations for the handling of tame elephants that have been trained to handle wild elephants that enter settlements in areas prone to conflict between humans and animals. From the external side, it is related to human-animal conflict and the illegal hunting of Sumatran elephants for their ivory and trade. According to a study, online trade in products derived from elephant ivory is quite high. In 2016 around 570 identified online sellers of elephant ivory with active sellers were found in Central Java Province. Convention on International Trade in Endangered

Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), the global regime governing wildlife trade, which Indonesia ratified in 1978, banned the trade in ivory and the poaching of elephants for ivory. According to the rules, elephants are included in Appendix 1, which is a list of all wild plant and animal species that are prohibited in all forms of international trade. While from the internal side it relates to the condition of the elephants that are captured and entered into the Elephant Training Center (PLG) which in the long term will affect genetic diversity and population structure. This is due to limited gene flow and an increase in "genetic drift" as well as the risk of inbreeding. And it is known that the biggest threat to Sumatran elephants is the conversion of forest/land functions which causes their habitat to shrink and fragment. As a result, Sumatran elephants live isolated in small colonies and find it difficult to meet between groups. Isolation that occurs over a long period of time is dangerous. Because of the breeding that occurs with relatives who are too close.

Therefore the Sumatran elephant conservation strategy at ANECC includes several steps and efforts that must be taken to maintain elephant populations in the wild and reduce threats to this species. Sumatran elephant conservation begins with the protection of their natural habitat, namely the dense forests of Sumatra. The forest area which is the natural habitat of the Sumatran elephant must be protected from human activities that damage and destroy nature. The existence of a good management plan is needed in efforts to conserve the Sumatran elephant. This plan includes strategies for maintaining populations, habitat requirements, and efforts to control human-elephant conflict. Communities living around elephant habitat must be given an understanding of elephant protection and the importance of preserving habitat.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The potential for Sumatran elephant conservation at the Aek Nauli Elephant Conservation lies in its capabilities elephants to maintain biodiversity around their habitat, strengthening ecological connections between different habitat types, and maintaining the balance of the ecosystem in the forests of Sumatra. Various Sumatran elephant conservation efforts, such as protection of natural habitats, preparation of plans management, community participation, education and campaigns, development of economic alternatives, and research and research, it is very important to increase the preservation of living natural resources in Sumatra. With develop an effective Sumatran elephant conservation strategy, the elephant population can be maintained Sumatra and its habitat, as well as maintaining biodiversity in Indonesia. Besides that, potential Sumatran elephant conservation can provide economic benefits through the development of ecotourism and environmentally friendly small and medium enterprises, so as to improve the welfare of society around the habitat of the Sumatran elephant.

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